

Title: China's Expanding Reach in Cuba: Intelligence, Digital Control, and U.S. Security Implications

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17069476

URL: <https://sentineljournal.substack.com/p/chinas-expanding-reach-in-cuba>

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the evolving strategic partnership between China and Cuba, arguing that American complacency regarding the island nation poses a renewed threat to U.S. national security and hemispheric influence. While the Cuban Missile Crisis is often remembered as a resolved Cold War episode, Cuba's deepening ties with China—its most formidable global adversary—signal a contemporary challenge with far-reaching implications. The analysis traces the historical trajectory of Sino-Cuban relations, highlighting ideological convergence, economic interdependence, and expanding military and intelligence cooperation. In particular, Cuba's geographic proximity to critical U.S. infrastructure makes it an ideal platform for Chinese signals intelligence (SIGINT) operations. The paper also explores how China's presence in Cuba contributes to the export of digital authoritarianism, undermining civil liberties and democratic norms. It concludes by urging a recalibration of U.S. policy: one that combines counterintelligence efforts with strategic investment in Cuban civil society to offer a credible democratic alternative to Beijing's authoritarian model.

KEYWORDS: Sino-Cuban relations; Signals intelligence (SIGINT); Chinese global strategy; Digital authoritarianism; Belt and Road Initiative (BRI); U.S. national security; Latin America geopolitics; Strategic infrastructure; Authoritarian influence; Cuba-China alliance; Hemispheric competition; Counterintelligence strategy; Civil society engagement; Democratic alternatives; Geoeconomic leverage

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Americans today remember the Cuban Missile Crisis as a nightmare, a crisis averted, and above all a threat firmly set in the past. But Cuba's close ties to the U.S.'s biggest adversary, China, makes its Cuban complacency a dangerous mindset that could not be farther from the truth. After the fall of the Soviet Union, China filled its shoes as Cuba's strongest ally and has only intensified their partnership in recent years. As Beijing ramps up its pursuit of global intelligent-gathering capabilities, Cuba's ongoing economic crisis has left it in dire need of economic investment and makes the island a prime target for Chinese influence. Located just 90 miles south of Florida, Cuba serves as an excellent platform to conduct intelligence activities, posing a serious threat to the integrity of U.S. strategic infrastructure. If the U.S. fails to provide a viable alternative to China's expanding global reach, it risks ceding a critical sphere of influence in its own hemisphere. This issue also extends beyond national security: China's presence in Cuba enables systems of state surveillance and repression that directly undermine the freedoms of the Cuban people. To truly defend the civil liberties the U.S. claims to champion globally, it must step up and offer a credible democratic alternative to Beijing's authoritarian model. Preventing China from expanding its presence in Latin America through its alliance with Cuba will require a concentrated effort to bolster counterintelligence, counter digital authoritarianism, and reengage with Cuban civil society.

Strategic Convergence

As communist countries, China and Cuba share foundational ideological values that ground their political relationship. The Republic of Cuba has maintained formal diplomatic relations with the People's Republic of China since 1960, the first Latin American country to do so.¹ After the

¹ Mao Xianglin, Adrian H. Hearn, and Liu Weiguang, "China and Cuba: 160 Years and Looking Ahead."

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collapse of the Soviet regime thirty years later, China quickly worked to fill that void as Cuba's strongest socialist partner. The following three decades have seen a period of Sino-Cuban relations characterized by explicit political goodwill and bilateral relations, with various presidential visits and agreements on trade, developmental cooperation, and educational exchange.² This reinvigoration of relations has defined Cuban development in the twenty-first century. China has provided approximately \$7.8 billion in development financing to the island since 2000 and is now Cuba's top trading partner.³ These close relations have allowed China to embed itself in Cuba's economy through large-scale projects like the \$120 million modernization of the Port of Santiago de Cuba pledged in 2015 and Cuba's cooperation in the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI).⁴

China has also sought to strengthen its military ties with Cuba, sending its defense minister to meet with his Cuban counterpart, Raúl Castro, for the first time in 1999.⁵ After the PLA and the Cuban Revolutionary Armed Forces (FAR) signed a formal military cooperation agreement a year later, high-level exchanges between military and state leadership have become routine. China has also been implicated in illegal weapons transfers with Cuba since 2015, when a Chinese cargo vessel was found to be carrying illicit weapons intended for Cuba.⁶ Most recently, Cuban general Víctor Rojas Ramos met with the vice chairman of China's Central Military Commission in April 2024, where they reemphasized the countries' "everlasting and unbreakable friendship."⁷

² Mao Xianglin, Adrian H. Hearn, and Liu Weiguang, "China and Cuba: 160 Years and Looking Ahead."

³ "Global Chinese Development Finance," Aid Data.

⁴ "China Regional Snapshot: The Caribbean," House Committee on Foreign Affairs.

⁵ Matthew P. Funaiolo et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

⁶ Aidan Powers-Riggs et al, "Secret Signals: Decoding China's Intelligence Activities in Cuba."

⁷ Matthew P. Funaiolo et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

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China began to establish an intelligence presence in Cuba since its very first military visit to the island. News reports from 1999 suggest that the two countries signed a deal giving China access to former Soviet signals intelligence (SIGINT) stations on the island in return for upgraded signal jamming equipment, with the intention of interfering with U.S. radio broadcasts.⁸ These intelligence ties have only strengthened over time, with the Biden administration confirming reports from June 2023 that Cuba has agreed to allow China to build an electronic eavesdropping facility in exchange for several billion dollars.⁹ The countries' ideological ties help create a mutually beneficial relationship in which China shares its equipment and technical training, while Cuba provides a presence on the island.¹⁰ These decades-long developments emphasize how China has a long-term commitment to developing a strong and comprehensive alliance and presence on the island.

Modern Developments and Geopolitical Implications

In the past five years, various shocks to the Cuban economy have left the island nation in a devastating economic downturn. The Covid-19 pandemic decimated the international tourism industry. At the same time, President Trump reinstated tough economic sanctions and restricted remittances from Cubans living abroad. Together, these actions wiped out key sources of international revenue.¹¹ To make things worse, the economic implosion of Cuba's close trading partner Venezuela has increased oil prices and left Cuba increasingly alone on the international stage with few friends in the largely U.S. allied region of Latin America.¹² The Cuban

⁸ Pablo Alfonso, "China instala dos bases de comunicación de Cuba."

⁹ Warren P. Strobil and Gordon Lubold, "Cuba to Host Secret Chinese Spy Base Focusing on U.S."

¹⁰ "Security Implications of the China-Cuba Alliance," Global Americans.

¹¹ Matthew P. Funaiolo et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

¹² Carmelo Mesa-Lago, "Cuba's Economy in Times of Crisis."

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government's system of state ownership has done little to mitigate this crisis, with government cuts to fuel subsidies increasing the price of gas by more than 400%. The resulting crisis has caused daily power outages, shortages of basic goods, and double-digit inflation that has forced around 10% of the population to flee the island.¹³

Cuba's desperate economic condition has created a strategic opening for China. The island's urgent need for external support offers Beijing a timely chance to deepen its influence, particularly given Cuba's prime location in the Caribbean, a region central to China's expanding global intelligence ambitions. While continued partnership with China could bring Havana a much-needed influx of cash, it also introduces significant risks for the island nation. Without alternative sources of revenue or trade partners, Cuba risks becoming economically dependent. It also risks an increased diplomatic backlash from the United States, as tensions continue to increase with Beijing. But with the U.S. continuing to impose strict sanctions and limiting the economic and political relationship between the countries, Cuba has nowhere else to turn.

The ongoing relationship with Cuba is also essential for China's broader development framework in Latin America as Beijing aims to expand its sphere of influence in the region. China is now South America's largest trading partner, second only to the U.S. for Latin America as a whole, and trade with China in the region could exceed \$700 billion by 2035.¹⁴ China is also investing heavily in strategic infrastructure in the region, with more than twenty Latin American countries signed on to the BRI and 37 multimillion dollar port projects in key places like Kingston,

¹³ Matthew P. Funaiole et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

¹⁴ Diana Roy, "China's Growing Influence in Latin America."

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Jamaica and the Panama Canal.¹⁵ These substantial investments further China's economic inroads in the region, allowing Beijing to present itself as a viable alternative partner to Western powers. Although increased aid, investment, and trade is beneficial to the region in many ways, Latin American leaders have raised concerns around dual-use infrastructure, where developments in port facilities could be precursors to PLA naval access.¹⁶ Additionally, China has found willing partners in authoritarian regimes who use the investment to further suppress the democratic freedoms of their citizens. In Venezuela, for example, Chinese telecommunications company ZTE collaborated with the government to roll out "fatherland cards," smart ID cards that collect and centralize personal behavioral data.¹⁷ Through this strategic investment and partnership with authoritarian friendly regimes, China is exporting not just capital but also models of digital authoritarianism and political control. This lens of global competition makes the developments in Cuba much more troubling.

The Signals Intelligence Threat

Signals intelligence (SIGINT) involves intercepting communications and electronic signals from both civilian and military sources, including transmissions via satellite networks, undersea fiber-optic cables, and radio frequencies.¹⁸ Capturing this data requires specialized equipment such as pole and parabolic antennas or radar systems. Geography plays a critical role in the effectiveness of SIGINT operations, with satellite interception dependent on having a physical downlink facility located within the satellite's coverage area and radar systems requiring a clear line of sight to their

¹⁵ Henry Ziemer, Jaehyun Han and Aidan Powers-Riggs "No Safe Harbor: Evaluating the Risk of China's Port Projects in Latin America and the Caribbean."

¹⁶ Diana Roy, "China's Growing Influence in Latin America."

¹⁷ Angus Berwick, "How ZTE helps Venezuela create China-style social control."

¹⁸ Aidan Powers-Riggs et al, "Secret Signals: Decoding China's Intelligence Activities in Cuba."

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target.¹⁹ Cuba's close proximity to the United States and its position along vital communication routes make it a particularly valuable location for SIGINT intelligence operations. The southeastern seaboard holds a multitude of space launch centers, military bases and testing sites such as the U.S. Southern Command, Cape Canaveral and Guantanamo Bay, all of which are vulnerable to the collection of sensitive U.S. military and national security information.

Figure 1: Locations of Cuban SIGINT Sites with Potential Ties to China

Source: Authors' research.

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U.S. adversaries have capitalized on Cuba's geographic proximity to the U.S. for gathering signals intelligence since the Cold War era, during which the USSR built its largest overseas intelligence site just south of Havana. Since replacing the Soviet Union as Cuba's largest communist benefactor, China is poised to take advantage of that same spatial dimension. The Center for Strategic & International Studies outline four likely sites of Chinese intelligence activity in Cuba, equipped with a variety of SIGINT instrumentation and physical security. Satellite

¹⁹ Aidan Powers-Riggs et al, "Secret Signals: Decoding China's Intelligence Activities in Cuba."

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imagery suggests that a complex formerly housing Soviet nuclear weapons in Bejucal, just outside of Havana, is now an operational SIGINT facility. This facility is equipped with dish, vertical, and horizontal antennas capable of collecting information on the flight paths and telemetry data on U.S. rocket launches from Cape Canaveral Space Force Station and Kennedy Space Center.²⁰ Studying launches from two of the U.S.'s foremost satellite launch sites would give China invaluable information on American space technology, potentially aiding the replication of both missile and orbital technologies. This supports its broader goals of catching up to, and eventually surpassing, U.S. capabilities in space, a core pillar of the PLA's modernization strategy.

Two other known SIGINT sites are similarly situated just outside of Havana. Known as Wajay and Calabazar, their infrastructures include large dish antennas array capable of intercepting satellite communications and mobile circular arrays used to triangulate the direction of signals.²¹ These developments expose both civilian and military information communicated via satellite in the region to interception and collection by foreign agents. Additionally, this equipment would help China better track its own satellites and spacecraft on the far side of the globe, as a global network of ground stations is needed to maintain telemetry, tracking, and command on assets in space. This contributes to the PLA's vision of space dominance by enabling better command, control, and communication and ensuring real-time response capability in contested regions.

In the far eastern province of the island in an area known as El Salao, a circularly disposed antenna array (CDAA) has been under construction since 2021.²² This form of antenna has been

²⁰ Matthew P. Funaiolo et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

²¹ Matthew P. Funaiolo et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

²² Matthew P. Funaiolo et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

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used to determine the origin of incoming radio signals since the Cold War but is becoming obsolete with the transition of sensitive military communication to more secure pathways like fiber-optic cable or satellite. However, by intercepting even seemingly routine high-frequency radio signals, the facility's close proximity to the U.S. Naval Base at Guantánamo Bay could allow it to collect information that helps build a detailed understanding of U.S. and allied military activity in the Caribbean.²³ Additionally, these antenna are only two miles away from a cement plant financed by the Chinese expansion of a nearby port. This proximity suggests a broader infrastructure strategy that combines economic development with potential intelligence-gathering capabilities.

Together, these advancements in SIGINT facilities in Cuba represent a dangerous extension of China's intelligence and surveillance reach into American territory. These low-cost, high-value antenna arrays and system give the PLA critical inputs on Americans satellite communications, radio transmissions, and launch telemetry that significantly weaken U.S. space and naval strategy in the region. By revealing the capabilities and movements of American assets, China can develop countermeasures and target forces more effectively, eroding American political and military control in the Caribbean.

Control Infrastructure and Digital Authoritarianism

China's intelligence threat in Cuba is further amplified by its dominant telecommunications presence on the island and support of the island's repressive regime. By integrating Chinese tech firms into Cuban networks, Beijing is capable of embedding surveillance directly into digital infrastructure while supporting the Cuban regime's control of civil society. Known as digital authoritarianism, this approach is the newest iteration of repression by authoritarian leaders.

²³ Matthew P. Funaiolo et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

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Extending beyond traditional surveillance digital authoritarianism aims to control and monitor civil society while proactively repressing dissent. Using tools like mass data collection, internet censorship, and state-controlled telecommunications infrastructures, authoritarian regimes are able to optimize systems of oppression and maintain regime control.²⁴

China has perfected this system within its own borders and is now actively exporting its model to other repressive regimes around the world, including Cuba. Chinese tech companies Huawei, TP-Link, and ZTE are the primary technology providers for Etescsa, the state company that controls internet access on the island.²⁵ Through its influence in the telecommunications sector, China has been able to install surveillance tools that permeate all of civil society. The Cuban regime has used these technologies to filter web searches and even shut down internet and telephone services during large-scale demonstrations against the government in July 2021.²⁶ Paired with similar initiatives in Venezuela, Uganda, and Serbia, these developments are a worrying sign of a global shift toward Chinese-defined norms of cyber sovereignty, where state control overrides open communication.²⁷

China's deep integration into Cuban networks only serves to enhance its signals intelligence operations. The embedding of Chinese surveillance systems in the region expands its ability to collect regional intelligence on dissident groups, Latin American governments, or U.S. activities. This raises the possibility of a Pan-Latin digital surveillance network with devastating consequences for the U.S. priorities of democracy and free trade in the region. Chinese digital

²⁴ Valentin Weber, "Data-Centric Authoritarianism."

²⁵ Leland Lazarus and Evan Ellis, "How China Helps the Cuban Regime Stay Afloat and Shut Down Protests."

²⁶ Leland Lazarus and Evan Ellis, "How China Helps the Cuban Regime Stay Afloat and Shut Down Protests."

²⁷ Steven Feldstein, "When It Comes to Digital Authoritarianism, China is a Challenge—But Not the Only Challenge."

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authoritarianism isn't just suppressing Cubans; it's building a surveillance ecosystem that enhances China's intelligence reach and undermines U.S. influence and democratic values in the region and beyond.

Policy Recommendations

To counter Chinese influence in Latin America, the U.S. needs to devote greater attention to the strategic competition and cybercommunications security in the region. Instead of using coercive methods to force the Chinese out, the U.S. should focus on offering viable alternatives to authoritarian models of development and supporting Cuban civil society while bolstering domestic counterintelligence efforts. These initiatives would work to restore U.S. credibility and influence in the region while deterring further escalation.

First, both military and civilian organizations must be aware of the SIGINT threat posed by Cuba and work to harden their infrastructure against interception.²⁸ Although most modern military communications are highly encrypted, private firms with equally sensitive information are more vulnerable to targets from SIGINT facilities in Cuba. Companies like SpaceX are on the cutting-edge of space technology that China has already targeted and must take steps to secure their system. This would be accomplished through initiatives by the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA), which builds awareness and competence for potentially vulnerable civilian companies.²⁹

The U.S. should also focus on improve cyber and communications access on the island and offering a democratic tech alternative to Chinese systems. The U.S. can support efforts to provide

²⁸ Matthew P. Funaiole et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

²⁹ Matthew P. Funaiole et al, "China's Intelligence Footprint in Cuba: New Evidence and Implications for U.S. Security."

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greater access to secure internet and virtual private networks through cooperation with independent satellite internet companies like Starlink and Project Kuiper.³⁰ On the international level, the Partnership for Global Infrastructure and Investment (PGII) has the potential to play a key role in combatting digital authoritarianism. Formed in 2022, the PGII serves as the G7 counter to the BRI and could be an avenue to develop competitive alternatives for development in Cuba. The U.S. Congress should support this initiative with adequate funding and prioritize investments in digital infrastructure.³¹ These proactive responses empower civil society and reduce China's access to information space.

Finally, the U.S. must reengage with Cuban civil society through support of the Cuban private sector and economic recovery. After decades of harsh economic policy that has done little to change the Cuban government's stance on human rights, relaxing U.S. sanctions would help private sector growth and raise the living standard of the Cuban people.³² Given the U.S.'s unique cultural ties with the island, an expansion of commercial and cultural engagement is the only way to compete with Chinese influence. This might include the expansion of e-commerce platforms, cloud technology, and any initiatives that support Cubans in their aspirations for greater economic opportunities outside of state-controlled means.³³ Sustained hostility towards Cuba and its people only draws the island closer to China, and the U.S. must take the initiative in resetting these relations.

Conclusion

³⁰ Ryan C. Berg and Henry Ziemer, "Exporting Autocracy: China's Role in Democratic Backsliding in Latin America and the Caribbean."

³¹ Doug Strub, "Confronting the Rise of Digital Authoritarianism."

³² William LeoGrande and Geoff Thale, "U.S.-Cuban Relations: A Realist Case for Pragmatic Engagement."

³³ Gordon Lubold, José de Córdoba and Courtney McBride, "U.S. to Loosen Restrictions on Cuba, Reversing Some Trump-Era Policies."

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For better or for worse, the U.S. and Cuba's shared history, geographic proximity, and cultural ties have inextricably linked the two nations. China's presence on the island poses a serious threat to the integrity of military communications and sensitive technology, and the U.S. must work to combat this influence so close to home. China's presence in Cuba is also directly supporting the regime's repression of the Cuban people. The U.S. has a longstanding record of promoting civil society and human rights in Cuba. At this juncture, policymakers should recalibrate their approach to ensure that influence is exercised in service of democratic values and the protection of individual freedoms. For too long, the U.S. has viewed Cuba primarily as a pawn in great-power competition. That mindset needs to end. A more principled approach is essential to not only to heal the relationship between the nations, but to protect U.S. national security in a way that aligns with who it claims to be.